

Triterpenoids-XXX. The Structure of Barringtogenol E—A New Triterpenoid Sapogenol from *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn

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The fruits of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn were earlier^{1,2} examined in this laboratory and three new triterpenoid sapogenols, barringtogenol B³, C^{4,5} and D⁶ were isolated and their structures determined. The isolation of two new triterpenes, tanginol and barringtonic acid, from the heartwood of the same plant was reported later by Row and Sastry^{7,8}. It has now been possible to isolate two more new triterpenes from the ethanolic extract of the defatted branchwood of the same plant. The crude saponin thus obtained was hydrolysed following the method of Barton *et al*⁹. The neutral part of the ether extract of the crude sapogenin mixture on column chromatography over silica gel furnished two triterpenes. Detailed studies on the constitution of one of these compounds, called barringtogenol E (Ia), and preliminary studies on the constitution of the other are described in this paper.

Barringtogenol E, C₄₄H₃₈O₇ (molecular weight by mass spectrometry), m.p. 220-21°, [α]_D²⁵ +20° (CHCl₃), showed U. V. absorption maxima at 205 m μ (log ϵ 3.66) and 230 m μ (log ϵ 4.41), which were attributed to a trisubstituted double bond and benzoyloxy groups respectively. The presence of benzoyloxy groups was further shown by the bands at 1700 cm⁻¹, 1730 cm⁻¹ (>C=O stretching vibration of benzoyloxy groups), 1120 cm⁻¹, and 1285

Fig. 1

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cm^{-1} (C-O stretching vibration of benzoates) in the I.R. spectrum of barringtogenol E. On saponification, barringtogenol E furnished benzoic acid and barringtogenol C (Ib) identified by m.p., mixed m.p., T.L.C. and I.R. spectra. Thus barringtogenol E is shown to be the dibenzoyl derivative of barringtogenol C (Ia).

The mass spectrum of barringtogenol E shows the molecular ion peak at m/e 698 together with the ions at m/e 576 ($M-C_6H_5COOH$) and m/e 454 ($M-2C_6H_5COOH$) corresponding to the loss of one and two molecules of benzoic acid from the molecular ion. Elimination of 18 (H_2O) and then 30 (CH_2O) mass units from the $M-C_6H_5COOH$ (m/e 576) ion leads to the peaks at m/e 558 and m/e 528 respectively. Loss of 30 (CH_2O) and 31 (CH_2OH) mass units from the $M-2C_6H_5COOH$ (m/e 454) ion results in the peaks at m/e 424 and m/e 423 respectively. Retro-Diels Alder fragmentation¹⁰ of the molecule leads to a very small peak at m/e 490 (a). Elimination of one and two molecules of benzoic acid from a produces the fragments m/e 368 and m/e 246 respectively. Further loss of 18 (H_2O), 30 (CH_2O) and 31 (CH_2OH) mass units from the fragment m/e 246 gives rise to the ions m/e 228, 216 and 215 respectively. A fragment containing rings A and B occur at m/e 207 (b) which undergoes further loss of water resulting in the peak at m/e 189. An intense peak at m/e 105 originating from the benzyloxy group correspond to the ion c.

Fig. 2

It is clear from the study of the mass spectrum of barringtogenol E that both the benzyloxy groups must be located in rings D and E of barringtogenol E. Of the four available positions, C-16, C-21, C-22 and C-28, the C-28 primary hydroxyl group is shown to be free by the loss of 30 (CH_2O) and 31 (CH_2OH) mass units from the m/e 246 ion. On benzylation under normal conditions, barringtogenol E afforded a product which was identified as barringtogenol C tetrabenzoate (Ic)⁴ by m.p., mixed m.p., T.L.C., and I.R. spectra. Barringtogenol C does not form a pentabenzoate under the above conditions as the axial hydroxyl group at C-16 in barringtogenol C is known to be highly hindered. The above experiment clearly eliminates C-16 as the site for any one of the benzyloxy groups in barringtogenol E. Consequently, barringtogenol E should be represented as $3\beta, 16\alpha, 28$ -tri-hydroxy-21 β , 22 α -dibenzoyloxy-olean-12-ene(Ia).

The second triterpene, isolated from the branchwood of *B. acutangula*, has the molecular formula, $C_{42}H_{72}O_{10}$, m.p. 149-52°. It showed U.V. absorption maxima at 205 and 230 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.68 and 4.25 respectively) similar to barringtogenol E. Saponification of this compound furnished benzoic acid and a neutral alcohol (not isolated in a pure state) which on acid hydrolysis yielded barringtogenol C and arabinose (identified by paper chromatography). This compound is, therefore, a monoarabinoside of barringtogenol C monobenzoate. In all probability, this compound is an artefact obtained by partial hydrolysis of some parent saponin due to the short period (15 minutes) of acid hydrolysis⁹. Further work on this compound is in progress.

Incidentally, it may be mentioned that this is perhaps the first example of triterpene benzoates occurring in nature.

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